

A study of transition metal polyoxoanions as bleach catalysts in delignification of wood pulp

K. C. Dey^{a*} and V. Sharma^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Jamshedpur Co-operative College, Jamshedpur, Jharkhand, India

E-mail : kcdey_ru@rediffmail.com

^bDepartment of Chemistry, RVS College of Engineering and Technology, Jamshedpur, Jharkhand, India

Manuscript received 12 October 2010, accepted 02 February 2011

Abstract : The field of polyoxometalates (POMs), although a mature field, continues to attract the attention of new researchers. The majority applications of POMs are found in the area of catalysis. This review is based on the patent and refereed literature of applied research which summarizes the applications of POMs as an oxidative bleach catalyst in delignification of wood pulp.

The common process for bleaching of wood pulp uses chlorine which reacts with chromophores and residual lignin to form hazardous byproducts which pose a serious threat to the environment. The chemistry of totally free chlorine bleaching method is oxygen based. In addition to oxygen gas, hydrogen peroxide, ozone, per-acids treatments are used. During the past two decades, the uses of elemental chlorine free bleaching agent have been widely studied.

One alternative for improving the performance of oxygen chemicals is the application of catalysts. POMs used as reversible oxidants, offer a safe alternative to chemical chlorine.

An environmentally benign new technology based on salts of polyoxometalates and oxygen is being developed to bleach wood pulp for use in the manufacture of paper.

The goal of bleaching is to remove lignin from the pulp for use in paper manufacturing process. The process of bleaching is to remove lignin from the pulp without a negative effect on cellulose, for which delignification should be performed in highly selective manner.

The researchers have focused on POMs, used as catalysts in aerobic conditions of oxidative delignification. This review constitutes a general approach to the design of soluble transition metal catalyst for aerobic oxidation in water.

In this paper, the function of transition metal polyoxoanions as oxidative catalysts is vividly reviewed.

Keywords : Delignification, bleaching, POMs, wood pulp.

Introduction

Wood consists of mainly two biopolymers : Cellulose and a cross-linked methoxylated phenyl propane polymer lignin.

Cellulose is the key component of the natural fiber from which paper is made. It gives tensile strength to trees and papers. Lignin gives colour resistance to biological attack¹.

The principal aim in conversion of wood to high quality paper product is to selectively remove the lignin, without making any damage to the cellulose. Previously, to manufacture white paper, the wood pulp are bleached with environmentally polluting chlorine. Lignin which

colours the paper dark brown is removed from the cellulose fiber. In most of the developed countries, industry has moved away from the traditional chlorine based delignification processes because of the formation of hazardous byproduct chlorocarbon^{2,3}.

Delignification of wood is a remarkably complex process; it is one of the largest scale chemical transformations in nature and in industry. The most desirable bleaching conditions involve removal of lignin with little or no damage to the cellulose and other polysaccharides present in the cell wall of the plants.

Many alternatives to chlorine have been developed in recent years; few oxidative bleaching agents for wood pulp are successful in its effectiveness and economy.

Lignin degrading fungi secrete metallo-enzymes which oxidatively cleave the lignin polymers to water soluble fragments via single electron transfer step. Once the lignin polymer is broken down into water soluble fragments, additional enzymes convert these fragments to CO₂ and H₂O. Chlorine dioxide (ClO₂) is used in the industrial nation as an alternative to cheap chlorine bleaching⁴.

O₂ and H₂O₂ are other attractive alternatives to chlorine based technology both with respect to environment and economy.

The lignin can also be bleached directly with oxygen in presence of H₂O₂ or O₃ but this method does not remove all the lignin and the paper produced is pale brown in colour.

The first technology that selectively delignifies pulp fiber in water using only oxygen⁵ and produces no liquid waste or toxic byproduct involves the use of transition metal oxygen anion cluster, polyoxometalates as catalysts. The use of POMs as catalysts enables the lignin to be decomposed completely to CO₂ and H₂O.

Once the reaction is complete, POMs are re-oxidized with oxygen and are available for another bleaching cycle. Lignin is an integral cell wall constituent in all vascular plants including herbaceous varieties. It provides rigidity, water impermeability and resistance against microbial attack. There are many possible monomers of lignin. The type and proportion depend on the source in nature some typical monomers are :

(S)

(G)

(H)

Lignin which is an aromatic polymer consisting of syringyl (S), guaiacyl (G) and *p*-hydroxyphenyl propanoids (H) units.

In this paper a novel approach towards lignin degradation studies is presented. It is known from the literature⁶ that lignin bio-degradation requires not only oxygen gas (O₂) but also hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂).

During this delignification process transition metal polyoxometalates have been used as catalyst to activate H₂O₂ as a delignifying agent.

Discussion

The versatility of POMs derived from the fact that their sizes, shape, negative charge density, redox potential, transition metal compositions and other molecular characterization of direct pertinence to the catalysis of redox processes can be altered by synthetic routes. The use of POMs as catalyst in homogeneous process has been reviewed in recent years⁷⁻¹³.

A brief review is presented on the current ideas of the mechanism of the degradation of lignin by various bleaching agents¹⁴⁻¹⁶.

(a) *Chlorine water system* : In this system chlorine can exist in three different forms : (i) molecular chlorine (Cl₂), (ii) as hypochlorous acid (HOCl) and (iii) as OCl⁻ depending upon the pH of the solution.

(b) *Bleaching with chlorine dioxide (ClO₂) and chlorites (NaClO₂)* : O₂ and H₂O₂ are the most attractive alternatives to Cl₂ based technology both with respect to environment and economy.

In the bleaching process, the pulp constituents of cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin all compete for the consumption of the bleaching agent. A situation where the rate of lignin reaction is very high in comparison with the rate of cellulose degradation is most advantageous for successful operation. A convenient method for studying this ratio of reactivities was developed.

But a new environmentally benign technology has been developed by using polyoxometalates¹⁸ for selective delignification of wood pulp. This new approach is environmentally benign in four ways.

(i) It does not use any chlorine based compounds, thus avoids the production of chlorocarbons.

(ii) It uses only oxygen (O₂) as the terminal oxidant which is reduced to H₂O.

(iii) It uses no organic solvents.

(iv) All the organic byproducts derived from oxidative bleaching of the lignin are converted to CO₂ and H₂O.

Thus, this technology enables the entire process to be totally pollution free.

(i) The chemistry of delignification in pulp bleaching involves the following steps.

(ii) In this operation, the P_{red} and partially oxidized lignin fragment (Lig) are removed from the largely undamaged cellulose by filtration and washing.

(iii) The wash water is concentrated and any undesirable inorganic salts are removed.

In this step, the P_{red} is deoxidized to P_{ox} and dissolved organic compounds are converted completely to CO₂ and H₂O.

The overall process may be represented as

(iv) In this step, the P_{red} and dissolved organic matters are treated at high temperature under O₂ pressure.

This method forms an excellent basis for comparison between different bleaching agent and condition. A more thorough understanding of bleaching phenomenon would involve the chemical route by which lignin is degraded to soluble compounds. Work in this area presents several difficulties which can not easily be solved by studying actual bleaching systems. Some of these difficulties can be avoided by studying the reactions of wood lignin itself with bleaching agents. One of the outstanding questions in bleaching chemistry is concerned with site of the primary attack of the reactants. The bleaching agent may attack the guaiacyl propane unit either at the aromatic nuclei or it may react with three c-side chain of these units, depending on its chemical nature.

Structure :

POMs are a large and growing class of inorganic compounds composed primarily of transition metal ions in their highest oxidation states (commonly W⁶⁺, Mo⁶⁺, V⁵⁺) and oxide anion that comes in a variety of structures and sizes^{19,20}. Polyoxometalates having the Keggin

structure²¹ are generally used in acid catalysis²²⁻²⁵ due to their simple synthesis procedure and thermal stability. These acids POMs are molecular cluster formed by different metal oxide with the general formula [Xⁿ⁺M₁₂O₄₀]⁻⁸⁻ⁿ where X - heteroatom and M - addenda (W, Mo) atom. Heteropoly acids are ionic crystals in solid state consisting of large polyanions having primary structure [Xⁿ⁺M₁₂O₄₀]⁻⁸⁻ⁿ. This creates secondary structure by the addition of counter cation and water of crystallization. In addition, the arrangement of the particles, their morphology, pore structure generate the tertiary structure²⁶. The structure of heteropoly and isopoly anions can be described as MOn polyhedrons which are connected by sharing corners, edges and more rarely faces the important structures²⁷⁻³¹ of polyoxometalates are :

Type	Structure	Example
Keggin	[XM ₁₂ O ₄₀] ⁻ⁿ	Na ₃ [PW ₁₂ O ₄₀]
Anderson	[XM ₆ O ₂₄] ⁻ⁿ	Na ₁₆ [CuMo ₅ O ₂₄]
Dawson	[X ₂ M ₁₈ O ₆₀] ⁻ⁿ	Na ₈ [Cu ₂ W ₁₈ O ₆₀]

Synthesis :

Generally, polyoxometalates form in the solution from simple oxoanions and the necessary heteroatoms by self assembly process upon acidification³²⁻³⁵.

Most polyoxometalates have been prepared in aqueous solution. However, non aqueous and solid synthesis have also been developed. A few commonest Keggin type heteropoly acids such as H₃[PW₁₂O₄₀], H₄[SiW₁₂O₄₀] and H₃[PMo₁₂O₄₀] that are of great importance for catalysis are commercial available as crystalline hydrates.

Acidification is generally achieved by addition of mineral acid such as HCl, H₂SO₄, HClO₄, or HNO₃.

The heteropoly anions are usually isolated from aqueous solution by addition of an appropriate counter cation e.g. an alkali metal, ammonium or tetraalkylammonium.

The free Keggin heteropoly acids are sufficiently stable to allow crystallization from aqueous solution. These acids can be prepared by the classical etherate method. This method includes the extraction of the heteropoly acid with

diethyl ether from a strongly acidified aqueous solution of the heteropoly anion to form a heavy oily etherate of the heteropoly acid as bottom layer. The etherate layer is drawn off and decomposed by adding water under air stream. Then the product heteropoly acid is crystallized from the aqueous solution.

Limitations :

The activity of POMs is based on the idea that they react selectively with phenolic lignin structures in cellulose fibers and that they can often be regenerated with oxygen gas. Although POMs have widely been investigated they have not been applied in the wood pulping industry, most probably due to inefficiency and/or complexity of the processes. From the comparative catalytic bleaching with the two POMs $K_6[AlMnH_2OW_{11}O_{39}]$ (1), $[NH_4]_5H_4[PV_6Mo_6O_{40}]$ (2), it was reported that POM(2) catalyses more effectively the oxidation of carbohydrate than the oxidation of the lignin and hexenuronic acid. Thus POM(2) is not suitable for catalytic delignification on the other hand POM(1) catalyses oxidation of lignin and hexenuronic acid more effectively³⁶. It is also found that POM(1) used together SiMo reacts more effectively with lignin and hexenuronic acid than POM(1) and SiMo used separately.

Acknowledgement

The authors are very much thankful to UGC, Kolkata for providing financial assistance under minor research projects.

References

1. N. Mizuno and Misonom, *J. Mol. Catal.*, 1994, **86**, 319.
2. U.S.E.P.V. paper industry cooperative study : The 104 mill study, NCASI Technical Bulletin, No. 590, May 5, 1990.
3. B. Boman and B. Frostell, *Nordic Pulp and Paper Research Journal*, 1988, **3**, 13.
4. Chlorine and chlorine dioxide Replacement in Kraft Pulp Bleaching, 1992, TAPPI Pulping Conferences, TAPPI Press, Atlanta, 1992, Book 3, 1992, pp. 1209-1218.
5. W. G. Van, Beckum and G. J. Ritter. *Paper Trade* 105, 1937, No. 18, 127.
6. T. K. Kirk and M. Shimada, "Biosynthesis and Biodegradation of Wood Component", Academic Press, Inc., Orlando, 1985, p. 579.
7. A. Gasper, D. V. Evtuguin and C. Pascal Neto, *Appl. Catal. (A)*, 2003, **239**, 157.
8. A. Gasper, D. V. Evtuguin and C. Pascal Neto, *Ind. Engg. Chem. (A)*, 2004, **43**, 7754 .
9. K. Rwutlunem and I. Vuorinem, *Ind. Engg. Chem. Res.*, 2005, **44**, 4284.
10. K. C. Dey and V. Sharma, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2008, **85**, 1.
11. K. C. Dey and V. Sharma, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2008, **85**, 1.
12. K. C. Dey and V. Sharma, *Oriental J. Chem.*, 2008, **24**, 745.
13. K. C. Dey and V. Sharma, *Journal of Metallurgy and Material Science*, 2008, **50**, 53.
14. K. V. Sarkanen and C. W. Dence, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, **25**, 715.
15. K. V. Sarkanen and R. W. Strauss, *TAPPI*, 1961, **44**, 459.
16. C. W. Dence and K. V. Sarkanen, *TAPPI*, 1960, **43**, 87.
17. T. J. McDonough, *Pulp Bleaching. Principles and Practices*, TAPPI Press, Atlanta, 1996, p. 213.
18. K. C. Dey and V. Sharma, *Journal of Current Science*, 2008, **12**, 359.
19. S. K. Roy and K. C. Dey, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **68**, 398.
20. S. K. Roy and K. C. Dey, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **68**, 461.
21. J. F. Keggin, *Proc. R. Soc. (A)*, 1934, **144**, 75.
22. S. K. Roy and K. C. Dey, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1992, **31**, 64.
23. A. Korma, *Chem. Rev.*, 1995, **95**, 559.
24. I. V. Kozhevnikov, *Chem. Rev.*, 1998, **98**, 171.
25. M. Hartmann, *Angew Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 2004, **43**, 58.
26. M. Misono and T. Okahuru, *Chemtech.*, 1993, 23.
27. K. C. Dey and V. Sharma, *Trends in Inorganic Chemistry*, 2008, **10**, 23.
28. K. C. Dey and V. Sharma, *E. Journal of Chemistry*, 2008, **5(S1)**, 1021.
29. M. T. Pope, "Heteropoly and Isopoly Oxometalates" Springer, Berlin, 1983.
30. S. K. Roy and K. C. Dey, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1992, **69**, 224.
31. K. C. Dey and V. Sharma, *International Journal of Chem. Tech. Research*, 2010, **2**, 386.
32. T. J. R. Weakly and S. A. Malik, *J. Inorg. Met. Chem.*, 1967, **29**, 2935.
33. S. A. Malik and T. J. R. Weakly, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1965, 2649.
34. W. L. Jolly, "The Synthesis and Characterization of Inorganic Compounds", Prentice Hall, Inc, 1970, p. 460.
35. C. M. Tourne, G. F. Tourne and S. A. Malik, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1970, **30**, 3875.
36. Kyosti Rwutlunem and Tapani Vuorinen, *Appita Journal*, 2006.